

ISic1442

I.Sicily inscription 1442

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

tuff

(yellow)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Selinus

Place of origin (modern)

Selinunte

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Antonino Salinas, inventory 8781

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Αἰνέας

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285091

EDR 120821

EDCS 41300047

PHI 175658

Bibliography

Dubois, L. 1989. Inscriptions grecques dialectales de Sicile : contribution à l'étude du vocabulaire grec colonial. Rome. At 43 (<http://www.persee.fr/doc/>

efr_0000-0000_1989_cat_119_1)

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1973. Iscrizioni greche lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelika* 6. Palermo. At 63

Arena, R. 1996. Iscrizioni Greche Archaiche di Sicilia e Magna Grecia. Iscrizioni di Sicilia. I. Iscrizioni di Megara Iblea e Selinunte. Pisa. At no.45

Calder, W. M. 1964. Further notes on IG XIV 268 and other tufa inscriptions from Selinus. *Greek, Roman and Byzantine Studies*. 5: 113-122. At 120

Grotta, C. 2010. Zeus Meilichios a Selinunte. Rome. At 115-116 no.8 tav.28a

Famà, M.L., Tusa, V. 2000. Le stele del Meilichios di Selinunte.

Archeologia mediterranea e del vicino oriente 1. Padova. At no.3

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic1442. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4354029>